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Headspace solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography–mass spectrometry for the determination of volatile and semi-volatile substances in sebum as biomarkers for Parkinson’s disease

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the chemical components of sebum from Parkinson’s disease patients and a healthy control group using headspace solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (HS-SPME-GC–MS). This method requires minimal sample amount, minimal sample preparation and no extensive equipment. The extraction efficiency of six commercially available fibers was thoroughly evaluated. Among these, a 65 μm polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene coating emerged as the most effective for extracting key biomarkers: perillaldehyde, eicosane, and octadecanal. To maximize the efficiency of the headspace solid-phase microextraction procedure, several critical parameters were optimized. These included extraction temperature and duration, as well as desorption temperature and time. This comprehensive optimization process ensured the most suitable conditions for biomarker extraction and analysis.

The investigation included 80 subjects, comprising 28 healthy control group and 52 Parkinson’s disease patients. The compounds perillaldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal, which were first detected in this context by Trivedi et al. were investigated. Notably, perillaldehyde was identified as potential biomarker, while eicosane and octadecanal showed no significant differences between the two groups. Statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test confirmed significant differences for perillaldehyde ($p = 0.00154$). Method validation demonstrated high precision and accuracy of measurements, with confirmed intraday and interday stability.

1. Introduction

Humans can distinguish millions of odors which can serve as warning signals or influence social behavior [1,2]. Various diseases can be identified through changes in body odors part of which are volatile organic compounds (VOCs). For instance, the urine of individuals with cystinuria smells like rotten eggs, while the breath of diabetics has an acetone-like odor [3,4].

A remarkable discovery was made by nurse Joy Milne, who noticed a change in her husband’s body odor years before he was diagnosed with Parkinson’s disease (PD). In a pilot study, she was able to identify Parkinson’s patients by their smell with high accuracy using T-shirts they

were wearing. She described the smell of PD as “musky” [5]. Further studies revealed that this distinctive odor originates from sebum, the oily secretion of the skin. In tests with gauze swabs from the sebum of the upper back, the four VOCs and biomarkers perillaldehyde, octadecanal, eicosane and hippuric acid were attributed to the musky odor [6].

This change in body odor is thought to be an early symptom for PD [5] and it may occur years before the other typical motoric Parkinson symptoms such as tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia and postural instability develop. In PD, 60 % of degeneration occurs before diagnosis and potential neuroprotective treatments are more likely to benefit if the disease is caught early.

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In diseases such as PD, where a pathologically advanced stage has already been reached at the time of diagnosis, the presence of biomarkers at an early stage of the disease is of particular importance.

Already described biomarkers are, for example, prostate specific antigen (PSA) for prostate cancer and inflammations, cardiac-specific troponin T (cTnT) for the acute myocardial infarction diagnostics and neurofilament light chain (NfL) for neuronal damage as in multiple sclerosis. The most important biomarker and pathological feature of PD is the misfolded protein alpha-synuclein, which is deposited intracellularly in surviving neurons, the Lewy bodies [7–9]. However, alpha-synuclein was also detected in cerebrospinal fluid, blood [10,11], in skin nerves [12,13] and in the olfactory organ [14].

Recently, an α -synuclein-seed-amplification-assay (α -Syn-SAA) was developed to detect the misfolded α -synuclein (“ α -synuclein seeds”) in cerebrospinal fluid. This assay has a very high sensitivity and specificity and therefore allows patients to be diagnosed at the prodromal stage [15–18]. There are numerous biomarkers for PD such as UCHL-1, DJ-1, Parkin and PINK1 [7,9,19–21], but none of these markers are conclusive for the disease. Still, in the very early stages of the disease, it is difficult to diagnose PD. PD is a clinical diagnosis [22], although a biologically based classification has already been proposed [23]. A definitive diagnosis requires postmortem confirmation of Lewy bodies [24,25].

Non-invasive methods of sampling for biomarkers are preferred. One of these non-invasive matrices is sebum. Sebum, the oily secretion of the skin is a complex, lipid-rich matrix. It is secreted by the sebaceous glands onto the skin surface; this secretion is usually increased in PD patients, associated with increased production of yeast and enzymes [26]. One explanation proposed in the literature for the altered sebum composition in PD is that interactions between sebum components and skin-dwelling yeasts may modify the cutaneous microbiome, potentially altering the characteristic odor of the skin [6,27–29].

The forehead, and the upper back are described as particularly rich in sebum [30]. For sebum sampling, the upper back is the preferred site due to its minimal exposure to extraneous products such as cosmetics or moisturizers, thereby ensuring a more accurate representation of natural sebum composition.

Biomarkers encompass not only high-molecular-weight biological compounds but also include VOCs. Some diseases can be perceived by a characteristic odor, which can be described by one or more VOCs [31,32]. In the case of VOCs, enrichment from the headspace presents a valuable analytical approach. One possibility is dynamic headspace with enrichment on an adsorbent, such as Tenax. Alternatively, static headspace with enrichment on a coated fiber, known as HS-SPME, offers another effective technique. The trend is moving towards automated, solvent-free and miniaturized processes, to make them greener and more sustainable. Tintrop et al. gave an overview of various trends in sample preparation [33]. However, enrichment via the headspace is limited to a molecular weight of approximately 320 g/mol. The odorant with the highest molecular weight known to date, a derivative of the synthetic linear musk substance serenolide, is 324.50 g/mol [34].

Trivedi et al. [6] used for investigation a dynamic headspace method with enrichment of VOCs on a Tenax TA (Poly-2,6-diphenyl-*p*-phenyleneoxide) adsorbent tube and thermal desorption unit (TDU) on GC with

two parallel channels and simultaneous detection to the MS and olfactory detection port.

In this study, a HS-SPME-GC-MS method was developed for analyzing perillic aldehyde, octadecanal and eicosane (Table 1). This approach offers several advantages: it utilizes simple equipment, employs a straightforward sample enrichment technique, requires minimal sample quantities, and operates without solvents (Fig. 1). As hippuric acid is not volatile due to its chemical structure and does not enter the headspace when underivatized, it is not considered further below.

The SPME procedure was developed by Pawliszyn and coworkers [35–40]. Headspace-sampling techniques (e.g. HS-SPME) offer many advantages for sample preparation in the GC analysis of VOCs and semi-VOCs. Volatile compounds are separated from the sample matrix (e.g. serum, urine, sebum, saliva) prior to their introduction into the GC without solvent extraction techniques. Only minimal sampling handling is required. The HS-SPME method also makes it possible to extract and concentrate volatile analytes from small to large volumes of sample whilst achieving a high degree of sensitivity. This technique is used for many applications; e.g. for beverage [41], food samples [42], for bio-analytical applications [43] and environmental analysis [44], and to validate post-offence alcohol drinking claims in forensic toxicology [45–47].

HS-SPME-GC-MS for the detection of VOCs is already developed e.g. to monitor the effectiveness of chemotherapy for lung cancer and Non-Hodgkin lymphoma in urine [48,49], the diagnosis for pancreas cancer in serum [50] and the diagnosis of breast cancer in urine [51].

The aim of this study was to re-investigate the volatile biomarkers described by Trivedi et al. in the sebum of Parkinson’s patients and to develop a method that requires minimal sample amount, a minimal sample preparation and no extensive equipment. The study included 52 Parkinson’s patients and 28 healthy control participants, with samples taken from the upper back. Ultimately, the objective was to develop a routine test for the early diagnosis of PD, enabling early treatment and improved quality of life for patients.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents, standards and materials

Octadecanal from TCI Deutschland GmbH (Eschborn, Germany) was used. Eicosane and (*S*)-(–) perillic aldehyde were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Taufkirchen, Germany). Ethanol was purchased from Fisher scientific GmbH (Schwerte, Germany). Water was deionised. All chemicals were of analytical grade.

Agilent Technologies (Waldbronn, Germany) supplied the 20 mL headspace screwtop vials and magnetic headspace caps 18 mm with PTFE/silicone septa (maximum recommended operating temperature 180 °C).

Certified cotton fabric according to ISO 105-F09: 2009 (110 g/m²) as sample carrier for taking the sebum samples was purchased from testfabrics, Inc. (West Pittston, PA, USA) [52]. The size used was a piece of 2.0 × 2.0 cm, corresponding to 50 mg weight. Other sample carriers such as paper handkerchiefs Kleenex® from Kimberly-Clark GmbH

Table 1
Perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal as biomarkers in sebum samples from PD patients.

biomarker	structure formula	sum formula
perillic aldehyde		C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O
eicosane		C ₂₀ H ₄₂
octadecanal		C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O

Fig. 1. Analytical approach for the determination of volatile and semi-volatile substances in sebum as biomarkers for PD.

(Koblenz, Germany), unworn cotton T-shirts from Schiesser® GmbH (Radolfzell, Germany), gauze fabric from Paul Hartmann AG (Heidenheim, Germany), cotton pads from Shisara (Netto Marken-Discount, Maxhütte-Haidhof, Germany), swabs from Aptaca S.p.A. (Canelli AT, Italy), swabs OmniSwab from Qiagen (Hilden, Germany) and adhesive tape from Otto Office (Hamburg, Germany) were also tested for their suitability.

For the partial validation, a standard solution of 1 mg L^{-1} of perillic aldehyde, 10 mg L^{-1} of eicosane and 100 mg L^{-1} octadecanal was prepared in ethanol. The standard solution was diluted to concentrations of 0.50, 0.25, 0.20, 0.125, 0.10, 0.075, 0.05 and 0.025 mg L^{-1} perillic aldehyde and the corresponding higher concentrations of eicosane and octadecanal for the calibration curve and other validation parameters. The samples were prepared just in advance and measured within the same day. $10 \mu\text{L}$ of each of these mixtures were applied to a $2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ cm}$ certified swab of cotton, which was heated out for decontamination of interfering substances.

For selectivity testing, the blank certified cotton swabs (heated out) and the spiked cotton swabs were investigated. For the limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) the standard solution was further diluted to concentrations of 20.0, 12.5, 10.0, 6.25, 5.0 and $3.125 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ perillic aldehyde and the corresponding higher concentrations of eicosane (factor 10 to perillic aldehyde) and octadecanal (factor 100 to perillic aldehyde). Also $10 \mu\text{L}$ were added by the same procedure as for determining the calibration curves.

For stability and precision tests interday and intraday, $10 \mu\text{L}$ standard solution of 0.05 mg L^{-1} perillic aldehyde, 0.5 mg L^{-1} eicosane and 5.0 mg L^{-1} octadecanal were added by the same procedure. The samples were freshly prepared and measured on the same day, but for precision interday testing, the samples were frozen at $-18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis.

2.2. Sample preparation

Sebum samples were collected from the upper back on cotton swabs (certified material). On average, 0.4 mg of material consisting of sebum and sweat was obtained. Sebum samples from PD patients and healthy

controls were stored at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a refrigerator and examined as soon as possible, but no later than 72 h. The spiked cotton swabs for validation, the PD patient samples and control participant samples were investigated in the same manner: a cotton swab containing the sebum sample was placed in a 20 mL headspace vial. The samples were immediately sealed with silicone-PTFE septa.

2.3. Apparatus and software

2.3.1. Sebum sampling procedure

A digital push and pull force dynamometer, model AMF-50 (purchased from Amazon, unbranded, made in China) was used to take the sebum samples. Preliminary tests for sampling of the sebum samples from the upper back showed the best test results with a pressure of approx. $70\text{--}80 \text{ N}$ on average on an area of $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}$ and a sampling time of 10 s.

The sample was extracted twice by using PDMS/DVB ($65 \mu\text{m}$) fiber for 30 min at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for perillic aldehyde and immediately thereafter without opening the vial for 30 min at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for octadecanal and eicosane. Thermal desorption of the analytes for both enrichment temperatures was carried out by exposing the fiber in the GC injection port to $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 min. To prevent a memory effect, the fiber was held in the SPME fiber conditioning station for additional 7 min.

2.3.2. HS-SPME-GC-MS

Six commercially available fibers Stable-Flex polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene (pink, PDMS/DVB, $65 \mu\text{m}$), fused silica polydimethylsiloxane (red, PDMS $100 \mu\text{m}$) Stable-Flex carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (blue, CAR/PDMS, $85 \mu\text{m}$), Stable-Flex carbowax/divinylbenzene (orange, CW/DVB, $65 \mu\text{m}$), Stable-Flex divinylbenzene/carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (grey, DVB/CAR/PDMS, $50/30 \mu\text{m}$) and fused silica polyacrylate (white, PA $85 \mu\text{m}$) were purchased from Supelco (Taufkirchen, Germany). Before use, each fiber was conditioned in the GC injection port under helium flow in accordance with the temperature and time recommended by the manufacturer. Fiber blanks were run periodically to ensure the absence of contamination or

carryover.

The HS-SPME-GC-MS method was performed on an Agilent GC 7890 A with a 5975C mass selective detector with electron impact (EI) ionization (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and a CTC CombiPAL™ automated sampler, equipped with an SPME unit and a thermostated rotary oven (Zwingen, Switzerland).

The SPME experiments were carried out using StableFlex Polydimethylsiloxane/Divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB, 65 µm) fibers from Supelco. The standard Chemstation software supplied by the manufacturer was used for data acquisition and analysis. A HP-5MS, 30 m × 0.25 mm I.D. and 0.25 µm film thickness (J&W Scientific, California, USA) was used as the separation column. The temperature program for perillic aldehyde started at 40 °C and was held for 6.45 min. The temperature was then increased at a rate of 3.9 °C per min up to 210 °C with no hold time, followed by a rapid increase of 15.5 °C per min to 220 °C, where it was held for 15 min. The total run time was 65.68 min.

The temperature program for octadecanal and eicosane began at 40 °C and was held for 6.45 min. Subsequently, the temperature was raised at 7.5 °C per min to 175 °C with no hold time, and then increased at a slower rate of 1.6 °C per min to 220 °C, where it was held for 13 min. The total run time was 65.58 min. The temperatures for the injection port and detector were set at 250 and 280 °C, respectively. Splitless injection mode (splitless time 3 min) and helium with a flow rate of 1.5 mL min⁻¹ as carrier gas were used. Furthermore, a splitless injection sleeve (2.0 mm I.D.) for SPME applications was utilized.

All investigations (optimization, validation and sebum samples from PD patients and the healthy control group (CG) were recorded by measuring the total ion chromatogram (TIC) in full scan mode with a scan range of *m/z* 33–400 and the selected ion monitoring (SIM) simultaneously. The full scan mode was used to determine retention times and characteristic mass fragments and to search for unknown compounds or possible metabolites in the mass spectra. For evaluation, diagnostic mass fragments from the selected ion monitoring of perillic aldehyde (*m/z* = 107, 122 and 135), of octadecanal (*m/z* = 208, 222, 250 and 268) and of eicosane (*m/z* = 197, 253 and 282), and for quantification, the diagnostic mass fragments 122 (perillic aldehyde), 222 (octadecanal), 282 (eicosane), were selected.

No deuterated internal standard is commercially available for perillic aldehyde. Therefore, for validation experiments, absolute amounts of the three analytes were added and absolute peak areas were used.

Due to the heterogeneity of the sebum at a comparable contact pressure (approx. 70 g), it seemed reasonable to standardize the absolute peak areas of the target ions. For the original sebum samples, the relative peak areas of the analytes of interest were determined by dividing the peak areas of the corresponding diagnostic mass fragments by the overall integral of the total ion chromatogram.

2.4. Study group

The study included 52 patients with PD and 28 participants in a healthy CG. This study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee at the University Clinic of the TU Dresden University of Technology (application number: EK 262082010).

There was no difference regarding age among healthy participants and participants with PD.

However, there were more women in the CG and more men in the patient group. Participants in the healthy CG showed no abnormalities in relation to PD and had no family history of neurodegenerative disorders. The study group was comprised of participants in a cross-sectional study on olfactory and gustatory diagnostics in various diseases with loss of smell and taste, such as PD, conducted by the Smell and Taste Clinic, Department of Otorhinolaryngology of the TU Dresden University of Technology.

2.5. Method validation and statistics

Statistical validation was performed using SQS2.0 (Perkin-Elmer, Shelton, CT, USA) and Valistat 2.0 (Arvecon GmbH, Walldorf, Germany) software. The analysis was conducted on a standard solution mix containing perillic aldehyde, octadecanal, and eicosane using the previously described methods. All statistical parameters, including limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), correlation coefficient (*r*), determination coefficient (*R*²), relative standard deviations (RSD) for intraday and interday precision, and linear range, were evaluated according to the German standard procedure (DIN 32645) of the German Society of Toxicological and Forensic Chemistry (GTFCh).

Statistical analysis was conducted using OriginPro 2020b software. The Shapiro-Wilk test was employed to assess the normality of data distribution for both the PD patient group and the healthy CG. Subsequently, the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test was utilized to compare these two independent samples for statistical significance. The representation of all graphics was also performed with OriginPro 2020b.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Selection of sample carriers

The sebum sample carriers selected in 2.1. were tested at 50 °C and 120 °C (Fig. 2, A and B). As expected, the sample carriers at 120 °C extraction temperature showed higher blank values than those at 50 °C. There are qualitative and quantitative differences between the different sample carriers.

Decisive for the present investigations is not only the number of blank values, but also the blank values for the retention times with the target and qualifier masses of the analytes perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal. Without exception, all sample carriers showed high signals of blank values for eicosane and octadecanal. Without additional sample preparation, none of the selected sample carriers were suitable for analysis.

For further analysis, the certified cotton swab was baked in a drying oven (150 °C, 2 h) and extracted with EtOH/H₂O (*v/v* = 1:1) for 2 h in an ultrasonic bath and then heated in a drying oven (150 °C, 2 h), see Fig. 2, C and D. The best results were obtained with the baked and unextracted cotton swabs: no blanks were found for perillic aldehyde and octadecanal and traces of the target ion (*M* = 282) for eicosane were observed below the detection limit (Fig. 2, C and D). Consequently, the certified cotton fabric according to ISO 105-F09: 2009 (110 g/m²) as sample carrier with a bake-out time of 150 °C for 2 h was chosen for further studies.

3.2. Optimization of HS-SPME

First, the selection of the appropriate fiber was carried out. Six fibers (65 µm PDMS/DVB, 100 µm PDMS, 85 µm CAR/PDMS, 65 µm CW/DVB, 50/30 µm DVB/CAR/PDMS and 85 µm PA) were evaluated in order to obtain the best sensitivity and selectivity for perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal determination. The retention times were 26.94 min for perillic aldehyde, 35.69 min for octadecanal and 34.97 min for eicosane.

In addition, the extraction time in the GC injector port was 3 min, the extraction temperature was fixed at 100 °C and the desorption temperature was set to 250 °C. A compromise had to be found for the optimization, as only one fiber could be used.

Remarkably, both carboxen fibers showed the highest capacity to retain perillic aldehyde (C₁₀H₁₄O), although carboxen fibers containing carbon molecular sieves seem to be ideal for the SPME analysis of very small molecules (C₂–C₅) [53,54]. It is now common practice to use carbon molecular sieves consisting of a mixture of different pore sizes (micropores with a pore size <20 Å, mesopores with a pore size between 20 and 500 Å and macropores with a pore size >500 Å) [55]. This also explains the wide range of applications for these fibers. In accordance

Fig. 2. Chromatograms (TIC) of different sample carriers at extraction temperature of 50 °C (A) and 120 °C (B) and various prepared certified cotton fabric BW ISO 105-F09 at extraction temperatures of 50 °C (C) and 120 °C (D).

with the literature, the CAR/PDMS fiber is very well suited for the enrichment of VOCs (C3 – C15), such as esters, alcohols, alkenes, sulfides, heterocycles, carboxylic acids, ketones, aldehydes, phenols, amines and ether, e.g. in fermented tofu. Longer chain n-alkanes and n-aldehydes such as eicosane and octadecanal were not investigated [56]. According to our results, this CAR/PDMS fiber is not suitable for the enrichment of octadecanal and eicosane.

Although the DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber shows the best enrichment for perillaldehyde, it appears to be less suitable for eicosane. The PDMS-containing fibers (with the exception of CAR/PDMS) and the fiber CW/DWB are well suited for the enrichment of the longer-chain analytes eicosane and octadecanal. The PDMS/DVB fiber shows the highest extraction rates on average for the three analytes. Therefore, the 65 μ m PDMS/DVB fiber was used for all subsequent investigations.

The effect of sampling temperature on the extraction yield for perillaldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal was investigated from 50 to 150 °C using PDMS/DVB fiber (Fig. 3, A). For perillaldehyde, a maximum at 50 °C could be observed with decreasing headspace concentrations from 50 to 150 °C.

Eicosane and octadecanal showed a maximum at 120 °C. An increasing concentration in the headspace was observed at temperatures from 50 to 120 °C. At temperatures higher than 120 °C for octadecanal and eicosane, the equilibrium between fiber and headspace is shifted

more and more towards the headspace. This effect was significantly more pronounced for eicosane than for octadecanal. Therefore, two different extraction temperatures were selected: 50 °C for perillaldehyde and 120 °C for eicosane and octadecanal.

The extraction time of perillaldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal was investigated between 2 and 60 min using the optimal conditions previously established (Fig. 3, B). The time required to reach equilibrium was 10 min for perillaldehyde. The peak area remains nearly constant for thermostating times greater than 10 min. For the two higher boiling analytes, a longer period of time is required to reach equilibrium. For octadecanal, equilibrium is reached after about 45 min. However, the increase in peak area is minimal after 20 min of enrichment. The extraction yield of eicosane increases continuously over the whole time range investigated. Equilibrium is not reached within the investigated time of 60 min, but a shorter enrichment time is acceptable as long as it is reproducibly maintained. Therefore, as a compromise, an extraction time of 30 min was chosen for these substances.

An application range of 200–270 °C is recommended for the selected fiber, at which the analytes are desorbed in the GC. This range was investigated to optimize the desorption temperature (Fig. 3, C). Up to a desorption temperature of 250 °C, the peak areas of the analytes increase slightly to moderately. Despite the slight increase in intensities above 250 °C, a desorption temperature of 250 °C was selected.

Fig. 3. Enrichment of analytes at different extraction temperatures with PDMS/DVB 65 μm (A) and extraction times (B) with desorption time = 3 min, desorption temperature = 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and desorption temperatures (C) and desorption times (D) with extraction time = 30 min, extraction temperature = 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $n = 3$ each.

A range of 0.5–10 min was tested to determine the optimum desorption time. It shows that the peak areas of all analytes increase up to one min and then remain almost constant temperature (Fig. 3, D). A desorption time of 3 min was chosen.

In summary, the HS-SPME optimal conditions for the analysis of the analytes were as follows: 65 μm PDMS/DVB fiber, extraction temperature 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (perillic aldehyde) and 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (eicosane and octadecanal) and an extraction time 30 min. In addition, a desorption temperature of 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a desorption time of 3 min (splitless) were chosen.

3.3. Results of method semi quantitative method validation of HS-SPME-GC-MS

The validation results of the optimized HS-SPME-GC-MS method of perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal are listed in Table 2.

No interfering peaks with the same retention time as perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal were found in the sebum samples. The RSDs, both intra- and interday, between 3.4 and 12.3 %, indicate a very good and good reproducibility for perillic aldehyde and very good reproducibility between 4.6 and 6.7 % for eicosane and octadecanal of the method. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of the calibration curve from 0.991 (octadecanal) to 0.999 (eicosane) of the calibration graph emphasizes an excellent linearity in the investigated concentration range. The LOD with 0.04 ng swab^{-1} shows a very good sensitivity for this method for perillic aldehyde and one order of magnitude worse LOD for eicosane (0.68 ng swab^{-1}) and another order of magnitude

Table 2

Results of method validation with headspace SPME-GC-MS of perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal of the cotton swab. Validation parameters linearity, LOD, LOQ, precision and stability were analyzed following Peters et al. [57] using Valistat 2.0 software (ARVECON GmbH, Germany) [58].

Statistical parameter	perillic aldehyde	eicosane	octadecanal
Retention time [min]	26.93	42.96	43.27
Linear range [ng swab ⁻¹]	0.5–5.0	2.5–100	25–250
Equation	$y = 2276.1 \times - 201.9$	$y = 456.4 \times -$	$y = 57.0 \times - 1057.3$
R^2	0.997	0.999	0.991
RSD slope [%]	9.87	8.24	6.42
RSD intercept [%]	13.1	11.6	6.75
LOD ^a [ng swab ⁻¹]	0.04	0.68	7.38
LOQ ^a [ng swab ⁻¹]	0.13	2.27	24.87
Precision intraday ^b [%]	3.4	4.6	6.3
BIAS [%]	6.1	- 8.6	- 5.3
Precision interday ^b [%]	12.3	6.7	5.9
BIAS [%]	- 8.9	- 12.6	- 12.5
Stability ^c [%]	4.1	4.8	10.4

^a Limit of detection and quantitation were determined by establishing a specific calibration curve from samples containing the analyte in the range of LOQ. The limits were calculated from the residual standard deviation of the regression line.

^b Precision are expressed as RSD (%), intraday ($n = 8$) and interday ($n = 5$).

^c Stability (autosampler stability) are expressed as RSD (%), ($n = 5$).

worse LOD for octadecanal ($7.38 \text{ ng swab}^{-1}$, Table 2).

The total time for sample preparation, thermostating and analysis is approximately 96 min. Further time savings can be achieved by overlapping thermostating time and run time and by using a shorter separation column.

The validation parameter stability (autosampler stability) was also tested. The stability is between 4.1 % (perillic aldehyde), 4.8 % (eicosane) and 10.4 % (octadecanal). The autosampler stability is also suitable for the determination of the analytes.

3.4. Sebum test results

The samples were taken as specified under point 2.3. If the pressure was too low ($< 40 \text{ N}$), the signals were too low and if the pressure was too high ($> 120 \text{ N}$), the chromatograms were overloaded. Deviations were observed due to the different levels of sebum production among patients caused by the disease.

Sebum samples were collected from 28 healthy people and 52 PD patients. There was almost no difference in age between healthy people (63.25 ± 14.66 years) and people with PD (66.02 ± 12.18 years) (Fig. 4). In terms of gender, there were about twice as many women as men in the healthy CG (sex m/f = 0.56), but only about but only about 40 % of the patients were women (sex m/f = 1.60). The patients were diagnosed with PD on average 8 years before this study (7.63 ± 5.51 years).

Fig. 5 shows the results of the normalized peak areas of the target ions of the three biomarkers as violin plots. Normalization was performed using the total ion current (TIC) of the chromatogram. A semi-quantitative analysis was conducted.

There are outliers for all three analytes in the negative controls as well as in the patients (except for octadecanal, PD), each above the 1.5-fold interquartile range. In the case of octadecanal, there were frequent overlaps with other substances in the SIM mode, partly due to a high background. These cases (CG $n = 2$; PD $n = 5$) were excluded from the statistical analysis. Perillic aldehyde and eicosane also had one case each in the patient group, which was removed from the statistical analysis.

The outliers were not part of any particular phenotype. They were not people with a particularly long or short duration of the disease. Gender also did not play a role in the outliers, nor did medication use, if known. The analysis of outliers within the patient group revealed no abnormalities in terms of severity when examining both the Hoehn and Yahr scale and the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS).

The SHAPIRO-WILK analytical test was used to test for the presence of a normal distribution. This test is characterized by a high power with a sample size of $N < 50$ [59]. The results of this test are visualized in Table 3 (top) and clearly shows that the available data of the analytes do not correspond to a normal distribution, as the p -value is always below the selected significance level of 5 %. Due to overlap with other peaks, especially octadecanal, not every normalized peak area of the original

28 CG and 52 PD was included.

Therefore, the use of a parametric test would not be appropriate. The MANN-WHITNEY- U test, also known as the WILCOXON-MANN-Whitney test, was used.

For perillic aldehyde, the two groups differ significantly at an error probability of 0.05. This is not the case for the target compounds eicosane and octadecanal (Table 3, bottom).

The VOCs investigated here were discovered by Trivedi et al. in 2019 and showed differences between PD patients and the healthy CG [6]. Perillic aldehyde was significantly lower, while eicosane was significantly higher in PD patients compared to healthy subjects. Octadecanal was not significantly different but trended to be higher.

Our results show the opposite effect with perillic aldehyde. Furthermore, no significant difference was found for eicosane. Octadecanal showed no significant difference and no trend as well.

Although the LOD and LOQ for eicosane and octadecanal were higher than for perillaldehyde, sufficiently large signals were still detected in both the PD patients and the healthy controls.

The observed increase in sebum production among patients offers a plausible explanation for the elevated concentrations of lipophilic compounds. This phenomenon not only accounts for the higher levels of eicosane and the tendency towards increased octadecanal, as reported in previous literature [6], but also extends to the lipophilic perillic aldehyde. The enhanced sebaceous gland activity appears to create an environment conducive to the accumulation of these fat-soluble substances, providing a cohesive rationale for the observed chemical profile in affected individuals.

The differences in the relationships of perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal to Trivedi et al. [6] cannot be explained by improper storage of the sebum samples. The same authors investigated the storage of sebum samples over a period of 4 weeks at room temperature. No differences were found in samples stored at room temperature compared to frozen samples at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [60].

In the literature, a model mixture of 4 VOCs (with hippuric acid) according to Trivedi has been compiled for odor samples. However, these four VOCs alone cannot reproduce the typical PD odor, as odor comparisons have shown and additional VOCs appear to be of significant [61]. It can be assumed that other VOCs contribute to or make up the typical odor of PD. This would explain the different results to the literature [6]. In a new publication, alkanes, aldehydes and fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were detected, which possibly originate from a degradation of larger lipid molecules with further subsequent reactions [62]. At least the aldehydes might also contribute to the odor profile.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the volatile biomarkers perillic aldehyde, eicosane and octadecanal described by Trivedi et al. in the sebum of Parkinson's patients could be confirmed. A HS-SPME-GC-MS method was developed after method optimization, which requires minimal sample amount and

Fig. 4. Age pyramids of the study participants, left: healthy controls, right: PD patients.

Fig. 5. violin plots of the normalized peak areas of the quantifiers of perillic aldehyde ($m/z = 122$, violet), eicosane ($m/z = 282$, blue) and octadecanal ($m/z = 222$, green) of the healthy control group (CG, left) and the PD patient group (PD, right). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3

Results of the normal distribution test using the SHAPIRO-WILK test (top) and results of the WILCOXON-MANN-Whitney test (bottom) at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, CG = control group, PD = Parkinson's patients.

	perillic aldehyde		eicosane		octadecanal	
	CG	PD	CG	PD	CG	PD
number N	28	51	28	51	26	47
p-value	<	<	<	<	<	0.0020
decision at $\alpha = 0,05$	$\alpha > > p$	$\alpha > > p$	$\alpha > > p$	$\alpha > > p$	$\alpha > > p$	$\alpha > p$
medium rank	32.35	44.19	41.82	39.00	38.13	36.37
p-value	0.00154		0.60505		0.73448	
decision at $\alpha = 0,05$	$\alpha > p$		$\alpha < p$		$\alpha < p$	

a minimal sample preparation. This method opens up new possibilities for the analysis of low and moderately VOCs, especially in areas where sample material is scarce. It requires less extensive equipment compared to a dynamic headspace method with enrichment of VOCs on an adsorption tube and a thermal desorption unit (TDU). This HS-SPME method may be associated with a slight loss of sensitivity. Comparative data are not available.

The proposed analytical technique distinguishes itself through its simple sample preparation procedures, exceptional sensitivity for perillic aldehyde, robust detection capabilities for eicosane and octadecanal, and robust validation results across multiple analytical parameters, collectively positioning it as a promising scientific methodology.

The study included 52 PD patients and 28 healthy control participants which was more than in the previous study by Trivedi and colleagues. Samples were taken from the upper back. We were able to collect and compare data for all 3 analytes in both groups. We found a significant difference between the two groups only for perillic aldehyde which was more detectable in the patient group than in the healthy CG.

Data for all three analytes were collected and analyzed across both groups. A significant difference was observed only for perillic aldehyde, which was more detectable in the patient group than in the healthy CG. This finding suggests that perillic aldehyde may serve as a potential biomarker worth further investigation in relation to the condition studied.

Further studies with more participants are needed to confirm the clinical relevance of these biomarkers and to evaluate their application in practice, with the goal of developing a routine test for the early diagnosis of PD using a different and less complex method than described in the literature, ultimately allowing early treatment and improving the quality of life of patients.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Annette Zschiesche: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Thomas Hummel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nicole Power-Guerra:** Writing – review & editing. **Antje Haehner:** Writing – review & editing. **Björn Falkenburger:** Writing – review & editing. **Susanne Koch:** Investigation. **Jakob Broesamle:** Data curation. **Katja Schulz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Update

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Corrigendum

Corrigendum to “Headspace solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography–mass spectrometry for the determination of volatile and semi-volatile substances in sebum as biomarkers for Parkinson’s disease” [Microchem. J. 215 (2025) 114369]

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The authors regret that they missed to cite the BioRender software as the source for the creation of figure 1. The correct caption to figure 1 must read:

Fig. 1: Analytical approach for the determination of volatile and

semi-volatile substances in sebum as biomarkers for PD.

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The authors would like to apologise for any inconvenience caused.

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